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Towards The Discovery Of Identity: A Study Of Marcel Melthrorong's Novel Toghan

Abstract

Marcel Melthrorong is a Vanuatu francophone writer. He is the first ever Vanuatu writer to take up writing novel in French. This research paper is based on the study of his first novel Toghan which is inspired from his own youthhood times spent in New Caledonia. It depicts the oceanian youth who lost their identity in the struggle choosing between the Melanesian values and western model. This paper likes to examine how the novel brings out the circumstances that leads the protagonist towards the discovery of his identity in a society impacted by colonialism.

Keywords: Colonialism, delinquency, identity New Caledonia, Vanuatu

I-Introduction

Postcolonialism is a period after the end of colonialism. Post colonialism is the academic study of colonial history and its consequences. It is considered as "a disciplinary project devoted to the academic task of revisiting, remembering and, crucially, interrogating the colonial past" [Gandhi 4]. Post colonial literature dealt with the themes like identity crisis, loss of culture, nationalism, multiculturalism etc. People in postcolonial society had developed an identity that is a resultant of their interaction between different identities. Post colonial literature is a writing that focussed on anti colonial narrative and it gave a space to express the resistance to colonial past.

In general term, the quest for one's identity is a common phenomenon that strikes various sections of the society. But in postcolonial context, the quest for one's identity is the resultant of colonial effect on the society and globalisation. Thus today the quest for identity as a theme fills the space of contemporary literature in the world. Francophone literature is no

exception in this regard .Marcel Melthérorong ,a Vanuatuan francophone writer through his writing express his concern for the Oceania people who fall for western culture in the society where the impact of the colonialism is still present .This paper tries to explore the quest for identity undergone by protagonist of Melthérorong 's novel Toghan and how the realization of his own faults culminates in the discovery of his own true identity by the end of the novel.

II -Oceanian francophone literature

Oceania can be divided into four main regions: Australasia comprising Australia and New Zealand, Melanesia including New Guinea, nearby islands and archipelagos extending as far as Fiji via the New Caledonia, Micronesia grouping the archipelagos between Palau and Gilbert Islands and finally Polynesia gathering the most peripheral islands, from the archipelago of Hawaii to Tonga via the Pitcairn Islands and Easter Island.The literature produced in these regions are collectively called Oceanian literature.Oceanian francophone literature is rich and varied in new Caledonia with writers like Dewé Gorodé ,Jacques Claudine ,Nicolas Kurtovitch¹ and French Polynesia with writers like Chantal T Spitz ,Titaua Peu etc² .In Vanuatu ,Francophone literature is slowly emerging.Marcel Melthérorong is the first writer of Oceanian francophone literature of Vanuatu .In the novel ,he deals with his native country Vanuatu and New Caledonia ,a overseas French territory which awaits its referendum for independence in November 2018.

III-Marcel Melthérorong

Marcel Melthérorong is the first Vanuatuan francophone writer .He is born in 1975 in a native Vanuatuan family in New Caledonia He is also a singer, song writer, music composer. He did his studies at Bourail in New Caledonia. After having spent a year in prison for minor delinquency crime, he wished to change his life totally and thus he decided to leave New Caledonia to settle in Vanuatu to discover his native roots.

Upon his arrival, he didn't know Bichelmar or native language of Vanuatu .He felt detached. Later he had got to learn his native culture and language with great efforts and he involved himself in various social activities that in course of years helped him to retain a special place in the social milieu of Vanuatu. He decided to spend his time in the cultural life of Port vila . The Alliance Française de Port Vila sent him to Tanna to manage its branch in Lowanatom. Then, for a few years, he joined the Port Vila team and took part in the organization of

¹ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Litt%C3%A9rature_en_Nouvelle-Cal%C3%A9donie

² https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Polyn%C3%A9sie_fran%C3%A7aise#Litt%C3%A9rature

concerts and shows, large-scale events such as the Fête de la Musique and the FrancoSonik Nights. In the early 2000s, he was recruited by the Vanuatu Cultural Center to manage for two years a program for young people. Subsequently, he decides to devote himself more intensely to his artistic life. In 2007, he contributed to the coordination of the First Francophone Meetings, in 2008 to the organization of the First sitting of the Oceanic Arts and that of the 3rd National Arts Festival. He initiated the First Festival of the Arts of speaking. Since then his intervention is sought by Alliance Française for the coordination of major cultural and artistic events. Simultaneously, he creates with Monika Stern, a French ethnomusicologist, Tura Nambe, a music center. Marcel Melthérorong is an exceptionally talented musician. Singer-songwriter, under the pseudonym Mars Melto, he created two much noticed groups: XX Squad and Kalja Riddim Klan. This last formation and its musical center Tura Nambe have a common point, the expression of its desire to make dialogue between Melanesian and Western cultures.

He is the first ever Vanuatu francophone novelist. Toghán is his first novel published in 2007. In 2013 he published his second novel, Nagaemas. To recognize his contribution to literature he was conferred 'Chevalier en arts et lettres' by French ambassador to Vanuatu in 2013.

IV-Toghán –a semi autobiographical novel

Melthérorong's first novel Toghán published in the edition of the Alliance Française du Vanuatu gave him accolades by bagging the award Prix RFO du livre for the year 2007. Due to its success it was republished in 2009 with a preface by Nobel laureate and French writer J.M.G.Le Clezio who in an endorsement of the emerging writer, says "with Marcel Melthérorong, the francophone literature family is enriched by a new and original voice"³ [Melthérorong 5] In the novel, the writer recounts the events of difficult years in a kind of autofiction. He depicts the Oceanian youth who lost their identity in the struggle choosing between Melanesian tradition and western model imposed by colonialism. Melthérorong through Toghán who is the titular and the protagonist of the novel recalls his times spent in prison for minor delinquency. Toghán is a young adolescent born in a native Vanuatu family

³ My translation, Original : Avec Marcel Melthérorong, la famille de la littérature francophone s'enrichit d'une voix nouvelle ,original

settled in New Caledonia. He was sentenced to be in prison for getting caught while robbing in his friend's house along with his other friends. During the time spent in prison, he realizes his mistake and discovers his native identity which changes his mind and thus finally decides to leave New Caledonia to settle in his country Vanuatu

Melthérorong is so concerned about the youth who follows western way of living. He wants to teach the children the customs and tradition of his country. He sees the music, storytelling and writing as a means of conveying it to the youngsters and children. He says "I see music as a way of teaching my children and future generation on holding on to Vanuatu culture, our customs, our tradition at a time when western influence is changing our way of life." [Brader 110]. He sees writing as a tool of resistance thus he states the reason for him taking up to writing.

"Writing can also be a tool of resistance for our traditions in the past, because writing is timeless while speech is short-lived"⁴ [un vrai et véritable écrivain]

Marcel Meltherorong begins the novel with a short description of Vanuatu which shows his high regard for the country. He sees present Vanuatu as a "land where traditional ancestral values are still followed not so invariably than earlier, shaped over the years in keeping with the western atmosphere and local atmosphere. He is hinting at the impact of colonialism on the Vanuatuan society too.

Delinquency is the crime committed by the youngsters. Problem of delinquency remains an important issue in society. The teenage boys taking up to drinking, smoking, and other form of juvenile crimes are still prevalent in the society. In New Caledonia even now, Caledonian youngsters are committing such delinquency crime and the delinquency crime rate is high. Plans are framed to combat such delinquency crimes⁵. Meltherorong shares his personal experiences to make the youngsters realize their folly and to give an enlightenment about the Melanesian values of Oceania. The novel's title implies double meaning. Firstly it is the name of the protagonist and secondly Toghán means 'Big brother' that the author like a big brother wants to show right direction to his younger brothers or successors. The novel tries to bring out the difficulty of living in a foreign land. Meltherorong says "Tôghán "means" big

⁴ My translation, Original : L'écrit ca peut être un outil de résistance pour nos traditions dans le temps, parce que l'écrit est intemporel alors que la parole n'a qu'une seule vie

⁵ <http://www.europe1.fr/societe/hausse-de-la-delinquance-en-nouvelle-caledonie-renforcement-des-actions-de-securite-3593831>

brother "... It's a little me, it's a little New Caledonia, it's a little Vanuatu, it's a little neighborhood, the tribe, it's a little all the communities of Oceania. Tôghán is for all readers of Vanuatu and elsewhere, because I think that the problems are similar everywhere, the problems of integration in a foreign land⁶[un vrai et véritable écrivain]

V-A journey towards discovery of identity

Toghan was the third in a row of four children hailing from a native Vanuatuan family living in New Caledonia. He is wise, intelligent as well as zealous. He is not aware of his identity and he has no idea about Melanesian values. He spent his time with his friends. He enjoyed drinking wine. He involved along with his friends in stealing the car only to exchange it for a bag of weeds. They sell the weeds to those who are regular buyers in the street or to the teachers in the school. They will use the money earned to buy wine again. It is this kind of lifestyle that later made Toghan to commit crime. Finally it landed him in prison. Toghan and his friends is very inebriated on the night of robbery. When they pass by the the apartment of Eric, a friend of them who insulted them. They were very angry at him and they wanted to teach him a lesson. Out of intoxication they entered the house with the intention of robbing the house. They all were caught by police and were sentenced to be imprisoned.

The journey towards the discovery of his identity is initiated with his observation of co-detainers who were sentenced to imprisonment for different reasons like committing murder, robbery, drug trade. He finds there Giano and Doui who are detained for their involvement in procuring. They don't want to discuss the reasons for their detention publicly. Toghan who is guilty of his own offence is no more surprised of such kind of crime that led to their detention. He understands that 'the western model is inappropriate to the Melanesian lifestyle'⁷[20]

The real reformation of a person in prison is seen when he starts realizing his mistake. In the novel, Toghan recalls the night of robbery which was the reason for him spending his days in jail. He realizes his mistakes and his thoughts are obsessed with the regrets for his folly. He questions himself 'Am I guilty? He keeps on blaming himself by repeating words like 'My downfall, my prison, my oblivion. He thinks that he made his parents worried

⁶ My translation, Original: Tôghán », ça veut dire « grand-frère »... C'est un peu moi, c'est un peu la Nouvelle-Calédonie, c'est un peu le Vanuatu, c'est un peu le quartier, la tribu, c'est un peu toutes les communautés de l'Océanie. Tôghán c'est pour tous les lecteurs du Vanuatu et d'ailleurs, parce que je pense que les problèmes sont pareils un peu partout, les problèmes d'intégration dans une terre étrangère

⁷ My translation, Original :Le modele occidental est si peu approprié aux modes de vie melanesiennes

because of his action. He recalls how his father had quit drinking alcohol and smoking to work to feed his four children

The conversation between him and his sister Helly is an eye-opener for Toghan in the journey toward his discovery of his identity. When the conversation switched over to the routine of the street, his sister let him know how the youngsters waste their time drinking, consuming drugs as he was used to be. She uses this juncture to advise him to retrospect what is the main cause for his imprisonment. She makes him understand that he wasted his years of study and she kindles his mind on reminding of his inebriation on the night of robbery, when he is on denial mode of what she said about weeds. He couldn't know how to reply his sister but it makes him contemplate over the effects of alcoholism.

'The weed, the alcohol is only an excuse to avoid facing problem. The problems won't disappear anyway .it would perhaps stay there more than earlier'⁸[43]

Toghan is also getting aware of the effects of alcoholism when he get know about the reason for detention of Sefo who killed his cousin for insulting him of his friendship with Kanaks. Sefo says "Every small Wallisian community knew the true culprit of that murder .It was the alcohol"⁹

Toghan spends his time very productively in jail in writing, reading ,and playing cards .He finds pleasure in reading .writing poems.He writes poems about his times in prison and he writes note of memory about the sacrifice of the family in the revolt and he remembers the independant movement leaders who fought against the colonizers .Toghan too recalls an incident during his childhood days when the police fired against the people who protested for the independence of their country .When Joseph ,his co detainee narrates the memories of the incident in 1988 which ended with the sacrifice of independent movement leader like Eloi Macharo in 1985 has really aroused the mind of Toghan who had not thought of this earlier.It also helped him in getting aware of his Oceanian or Melanesian identity

David, the co detainee from Vanuatu is the main reason for the discovery of his identity and in determining his future course of action .When David knowing about the origin of Toghan ,starts to talk to Toghan in Bichelmar which is the language of Vanuatu ,Toghan wonders in

⁸ My translation ,Original: l'herbe ,l'alcool n'était que des échappatoires,des dérobades face aux problèmes.Les problèmes ne disparaissaient pas pour autant

⁹ My translation ,Original :Toute la petite communauté wallisienne connaissait le véritable coupable de ce meurtre. C'était l'alcool.

what language he is speaking to him .It is so intriguing to him and he wanted to know more about Vanuatu ,his ancestral country .David narrated him about the individuality of their country.He elaborated him about the role of each villager in the implementation of plans that the leader of the village decides to undertake and the rules framed to protect the sea .In the village ,the men gather with a cup of traditional drink kava to talk about the future of the village in contrast to the youngsters in the streets of new Caledonia who finds drinking ,drug consuming ,stealing ‘to kill the time’[41]in these places where the men gather around with a cup of kava for debating about the future of village ,the disputes or des rivalry opposing this or that clan’¹⁰[53]

Toghan now know about his identity and he made up his mind to leave for Vanuatu .His father visited him in the jail asked him what he is going to do after the release .He said he wanted to go to Vanuatu. His father is not in agreement with his son’s decision and he askshim how he is going to survive there without knowing bichelmar and the customs .He also adds that he couldn’t get any job and he would suffer as he did.He further asks him why he wanted to go there when he has all facilities here in New Caledonia .But Toghan replies that he wanted to go there to learn the custom and language. Despite his father’s hopelessness ,Toghan didn’t give up.He says to his father that he is firm in his decision to go to VanuatuJust to learn....all the tricks of there that you had no time to teach me¹¹

Toghan sees his idea to leave for Vanuatu as an opportunity to him to remake himself and to get a new lease of life in a new land which is native land. He wanted to be no more a part of the land

“He wishes to get amazed at himself, to get back on his foot, no more to get caught into the numerous traps of the consumer society which brought him to birth ,seen him grow.....”¹²[54]

Toghan has finally got released from the prison.When the officer says to him‘Next time’.Toghan replies seriously yet confidently that there won’t be another .He is happy of his release and he says “It is now that everything starts. It s now”[73]¹³

¹⁰ My translation ,Original:...dans ces lieux ou les hommes se ressemblaient autour d’une coupe de kava pour débattre de l’avenir du villages ,des litiges ou des rivalités opposant tel out el clan

¹¹ My translation ,Original : ...juste pour apprendre.... tous les trucs de la bas que t’as pas eu le temps de m’apprendre

¹² My translation ,Original :Il Souhaitait se surprendre ,se reprendre ,ne plus se faire prendre aux nombreux pièges de la societe de la consommation qui l’avait fait naitre ,vu grandir

Toghan finally left for Vanuatu as he wished and he could get to learn about his language and culture to assert his identity .By the end of the novel we see the accomplished Toghan is now an adult and the father of little Nial .The writer ends the novel in the same way as he begins the novel “It is in this part of the world were born the children of Toghan”[73]¹⁴.Clezio notes that “With Toghan ,Marcel meltherorong gave life to a hero of the liberty ,worthy to find back his ancient root ,because he has overcome the test and the injustice that is still relevant to his brothers of Grand terre.”¹⁵ [6]

VI-Conclusion

Marcel Melthérorong reached out to the youngsters of Oceania through this novel **Toghan** which is inspired from his own youthhood experience .Being a face of Vanuatu with versatility ,through his first novel he proves well his writing talent too .The novel lets the youngsters of Whole of Oceania to know about the Melanesian values,their culture and identity .Virginie Soula’s words should be noted ‘ It is the Pacific, the Oceanian culture that is reflected in each of the works, proposals ... These are common questions about languages, the permanence of a traditional culture in a changing world and related phenomena that are the acculturation, the search for identity, etc¹⁶[Entretien]

¹³ My translation,Original :C’est maintenant que tout commence .C’est maintenant

¹⁴ My translation ,Original :C’était dans cette partie du monde que naitront les enfants de Toghan

¹⁵ My translation,Original :Avec Toghan ,Marcel Melthérorong donne vie a un héros de la liberté ,digne de retrouver la source ancienne ,parce qu’il a traversé les epreuves et les injustices que connaissent encore ses frères de la Grande terre

¹⁶ My translation,Original: c'est le Pacifique, la culture océanienne qui transparaît dans chacun des ouvrages, des propositions... Ce sont des interrogations communes sur les langues, la permanence d'une culture traditionnelle dans un monde en mutation et les phénomènes connexes que sont l'acculturation, la recherche de l'identité, etc.

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